

TWO WALLS: EMOTIONAL MATURITY AND INTELLECTUAL VERSATILITY OF SCHOOL LEADERS

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Abstract:

This research was conducted to determine the level of emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders. The respondents to this study were the 97 school leaders from the northern district of Negros Occidental for the school year 2022-2023. The study used a mixed-method exploratory-sequential type of design. A modified questionnaire was used for data collection, and it was pre-tested for reliability using Cronbach's alpha reliability technique. The research instrument was validated using content validity with nine experts. The statistical tools used were frequency and percentage distribution, mean, and standard deviation. Results of the study revealed that the level of emotional maturity of school leaders was generally high according to selected variables. The emotional maturity of school leaders was generally high when they were grouped according to selected variables in terms of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. However, the emotional maturity of the youngest and most phlegmatic school leaders, along with the area of self-regulation, and the gay school leaders, along with the area of self-awareness, were lower than the average. The intellectual versatility of school leaders, according to the variables of groupings, was generally high. For the qualitative component, fast report submission, teacher misconduct involving work and school cleanliness, and activities overlapping were the most common reasons school leaders were stressed and weary. Fairness, efficiency, calmness, good communication with the school, and adaptability to challenging circumstances were the best approaches to managing emotions at work. Thus, school leaders should be positive, recognize that not all organizations are ideal, and always make fair decisions always. On the basis of the findings of the study, a psychological and competency-based program is recommended.

Keywords: Emotional Maturity, Intellectual Versatility, School Leaders

Introduction:

Emotions and knowledge were important in the workplace. Emotionally mature people try to see themselves in a better light and combine thoughts and feelings rather than worrying. Intellectually versatile people value inquiry and connections. Working was emotionally and intellectually exhausting, leading to stress or commitment (Anjali, 2018).

According to Fisher (2017), the experience of emotions as well as cognitive flexibility are related to job satisfaction, with the experience of positive emotions being related to increased job satisfaction and the experience of negative emotions being related to decreased job satisfaction. This means that employees who report experiencing positive emotions in the workplace also report greater feelings of satisfaction with their job than employees who report experiencing negative emotions in the workplace. The demands and accountability increased; there was a lot of stress, and school administrators felt that society overlooked their profession.

Oakes and Lam (2017) indicated that potential school leaders view the role as overly demanding, stressful, lonely, lacking support, and only for particular social groups. These effects and perceptions of school leaders may lead to a shortage and maybe a decline in applicant quality, except for schools in "non-challenging circumstances." They must be careful not to "eat the seed corn" by scaring off the finest and brightest from school leadership. This report supports school leaders' need to obtain training, although recent data reveals that most don't. The stages of leadership and program dimensions should be included in any school leader's professional development program. Similar to this, keeping talented administrators were the biggest difficulty facing educational institutions. In the workplace, emotional maturity and cognitive adaptability were becoming more important since they help predict how someone react and how they view their job. Hence, school leaders jobs and performance affect workload and employee behavior. Some school leaders are frustrated because they can't understand and control others' emotions,

leading to disputes with coworkers, bosses, and subordinates and little or no job satisfaction. They also cannot think effectively to make decisions about work. Thus, the researcher was personally motivated to explore the intellectual versatility and emotional maturity of school leaders and was able to suggest a psychological and competency-based training development plan.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the level of emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders in the Division of Negros Occidental for the school year 2022-2023: Basis for psychological and competency – based training development plan.

Literature Review

Emotions were an integral and inseparable part of everyday organizational life. The experience of work is saturated with emotions, from moments of fear, joy, frustration or grief to an enduring sense of commitment or dissatisfaction. A review on emotions in the workplace, (Ashforth & Humphrey, (2009)(as cited by Abraham 2017), emphasized how past research fostered the belief that 'emotion is the antithesis of rationality'. Ashforth and Humphrey argue that this belief is too simplistic, and that the experience of labor is saturated with emotion. Recent empirical work examining the relationship between emotions and aspects of work, and strain has referred to the work and introduced the concept of emotional labor.

Magulod (2017) explained that the congruity between creativity and emotional maturity is a way for teacher education institutions (TEIs) in the Philippines to benchmark necessary interventions in order to foster and cultivate creativity as an essential and desirable graduate attribute for 21st century educators. Outcome-based or competency-based teaching and learning call for the creativity and innovation of future teachers to become effective facilitators of 21st-century teaching and learning. Thus, strengthening the emotional intelligence of school leaders to connect, collaborate, adapt, and communicate will ensure creativity and innovation.

Brine (2019) expressed the reasons why the role of emotions in the workplace has generally been ignored. First, the workplace has traditionally been viewed as a rational, logical, and non-emotional environment, with its primary purpose being the completion of specific tasks, such that emotions have been considered irrelevant or even unnecessary to effective workplace performance. Furthermore, emotions were transient and difficult to assess using self-report techniques, so many researchers and practitioners tend to avoid this area of study and instead focus on more easily measurable constructs such as attitude or satisfaction. Emotions in the workplace have begun to pay more attention to affect, and due to an increase in the number of employees working in service industries, the demand for emotional expression in the context of customer service has risen. Finally, because of the popularization of the construct of EI,

Consequently, emotional maturity is the determinant of stress. Effective leaders, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, poor health, and workplace performance have been key areas for organizational psychology research over the past decade. More recent research has focused on the role of emotions in the workplace, and the development from this approach has been to conceptually examine the relationship between cognition and emotions in the workplace (Askanasy, Hartel, & Zerbe, 2020).

Methodology:

Research Design

This study used a mixed-method explanatory sequential type of research, which explained that this investigation tends to collect data in the field at the site where respondents experience the issue or problem under study. It involves philosophical assumptions, the use of qualitative and quantitative approaches, and the mixing and/or integrating both approaches in the study. The mixed-method sequential explanatory design consists of two distinct phases: quantitative followed by qualitative (Creswell et al. 2003 as cited by Oquindo 2022). In this design, a researcher first collects and analyzes the quantitative (numeric) data. The qualitative (text) data are collected and analyzed second in the sequence and help explain, or elaborate on, the quantitative results obtained in the first phase. The second, qualitative, phase builds on the first, quantitative, phase, and the two phases are connected in the intermediate stage in the study.

According to Calderon as cited by Alberto et al (2014) , mixed-method research design, it describes data and characteristics about the population or phenomenon being studied. This research method is design procedures for collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in a single study or in multiphase series of studies.

Additionally, the research design was appropriate for this study because it aimed to collect data or information on the phenomenon relating to the level of emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders during the

academic year 2022–2023. The survey questionnaire was used to assess the emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders. On the other hand, open-ended questions were used to collect the qualitative data. The survey questionnaire and review of relevant literature served as the basis for the questions that guided the open-ended questions. The study questions and reoccurring themes were used to analyze respondents' responses.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the selected 97 school leaders from the 2nd, and 3rd congressional district schools in the Negros Occidental Division for the school year 2022-2023. The school leaders answered both qualitative and quantitative questionnaires to determine the emotional maturity and intellectual versatility.

Sampling Techniques

Stratified proportionate random sampling was used to select the respondents for this investigation. More than 130 school leaders from the 8 districts in Negros Occidental were counted to calculate the sample size using Slovin's formula. To determine the percentage, the researcher divided the total number of school leaders by the total number of school leaders in each district, multiplied by the sample size, and then distributed the results proportionally across the several districts to determine the number of respondents per district. Additionally, the researcher tend to employ qualitative strategy instead of estimating the population parameters. Convenience sampling was used to select th respondents who are "information rich" for the study. The respondents' availability, accessibility, preferences, and willingness were heavily taken into consideration.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Division	Number of School Leaders	
	Actual	Samplle Size
Manapla	18	14
Toboso	26	19
Calatrava	26	219
Talisay 111	9	
Talisay 25	4	
Talisay 315	11	
E.B. Magalona 1	14	11
E.B. Magalana 2	13	10

Data-Gathering Instrument

This study used a modified questionnaire of (Gardner 2005) and cognitive flexibility tool of Dennis and Vander (2010) some of the statements were deleted and choose only the statements that suit the local setting which focused on the level of emotional maturity, and intellectual versatility of school leaders. To gather the necessary data, the researcher used the instrument which the validity and the reliability were duly established.

In this investigation, one set of survey questionnaire was used by the researcher to gather the necessart data. This was the questionnaire which was used to determine the level of emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders in terms of four variables. The data-gathering instrument that was administered to the respondents composed of two (3) major parts.

Part I was the respondent’s personal information which requires them to supply or check the needed information concerning their birth order, sexual orientation, take home pay and type of temperament.

Part II of the instrument was the questionnaire proper consisting of 25 items to determine the level of emotional maturity of school leaders. The items were answerable of a 5 point scale: 5 (always), 4 (often), 3 (sometimes), 2 (seldom) and 1 (never). The corresponding numerical value are converted into scales below.

Score Range	Interpretation	Description
4.50-5.00	Very High	The level of emotional maturity is always observed
3.50-4.49	High	The level of emotional maturity is often observed
2.50-3.49	Average	The level of emotional maturity is sometimes observed
1.50-2.49	Low	The level of emotional maturity is seldom observed
1.00-1.49	Very Low	The level of emotional maturity is never observed

To measure the level of intellectual versatility of school leaders. The 20 items were answerable of a 5 point scale: 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Neutral), 2 (Disagree) and 1 (Strongly Disagree). The corresponding numerical value were converted into scales below.

Score Range	Interpretation	Description
4.50-5.00	Very High	The level of intellectual versatility is most of the time observed
3.50-4.49	High	The level of intellectual versatility Is usually observed
2.50-3.49	Average	The level of intellectual versatility is often observed
1.50-2.49	Low	The level of intellectual versatility is occasionally observed
1.00-1.49	Very Low	The level of intellectual versatility is never observed

Validity of the Research Instrument

According to Thorndike and Hagen as cited by Bacomo (2019), validity is the suitability of the test for its purpose. It must yield the kind it needs. A test is valid if it yields scores that help accomplish the purpose for which it was intended. The developed modified questionnaire was presented to a jury panel composed of 9 experts in the field of education, psychology and research. The jury panel evaluated the instrument using Lawshe's content validity criteria. This validity tool was the most appropriate to determine to degree to which an assessment instrument is relevant what is intended to measure. The validators are researcher, professor, guidance counselor and psychometrician. They went over the research instrument item-by-item and judged the suitability and appropriateness of the item. Recommendations and suggestions for improvement were taken into consideration and were given due importance by the researcher.

Comments and suggestions are incorporated in the final copy. The result indicated that 38 of the 45 items have CVR of 1.00 while 7 have the CVR of 0.78 (See Appendix C). This means that experts were in agreement that the items were essential and were able to measure what the researcher intended to measure. Likewise, the experts were also in agreement that the questions posed in the qualitative questionnaire were essential.

Reliability of the Research Instrument

Reliability is defined as the degree of consistency and precision of accuracy that measuring instrument demonstrates. A data-gathering instrument is said to be reliable if it has the ability from to elicit stable, consistent and dependable data from the respondents (Guevarra , 2009).

To meet the actual requirements for the reliability test on the emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders, the researcher administered the 25 items for emotional maturity and 19 items for intellectual versatility for dry-run to 30 school leader who were from the District of Murcia 1 and 2. These respondents were not included as actual respondents of the study . The data gathered were treated and computed with the application of the Cronbach Alpha with the 0.899 for Coefficient Value for emotional maturity and 0.940 for intellectual versatility(See Appendix D). Therefore, the data-gathering instrument has high degree of internal consistency, hence it can considered as having very high degree of reliability.

Data-Gathering Procedure

To carry out the survey and the distribution of the questionnaire to the school administrators in the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd congressional districts that fall under the jurisdiction of the Division of Negros Occidental, the researcher first obtained permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) and the District Supervisor.

Following the obtaining of the necessary permissions, sufficient copies of the questionnaires were reproduced, and the respondents were personally given the questionnaires to complete. This was done in order to guarantee the immediate retrieval of all of the responses. The researcher also made an electronic copy of the instrument so that they could have a flexible and handy manner of gathering data, but it was up to the respondents to decide whether they would use the hardcopy or the electronic form. The study's aims were explained to the respondents, and they received guarantees regarding the privacy of their answers. The instruments were then collected, tallied, and evaluated by the conceptual framework and the specific objectives of the study.

To compute the quantitative responses, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was utilized. The investigation necessitated the data to be evaluated, tabulated, and interpreted by certain problems that were presented.

Furthermore, the interpretation of open-ended questions does not require the use of any statistical tools; rather, the researchers turned to thematic analysis to answer the specific questions raised by this study parallel with the quantitative questions.

Statistical Treatment

The following procedures were adopted to analyze the data gathered for this work in accordance with the nature of the specific problems raised.

For problem number 1 which determined the profile of the school leaders in terms of: birth order, sexual orientation, take home pay, and type of temperament, frequency and percentage were used.

For problems 2, 3 and 4 concerning the level of emotional maturity and intellectual versatility of school leaders when they were taken as a whole and grouped according to (a)birth order (b) family structure, (c) take home pay, and (d) types of temperament, necessitated the application of mean and standard deviation.

Scales of the mean and corresponding description were as follows:

Score Range	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very High
3.50-4.49	High
2.50-3.49	Average
1.50-2.49	Low
1.00-1.49	Very Low

For qualitative questions, the researcher made use of thematic approach.

Ethical Consideration

When designing the research instrument, ethical considerations had to be taken into account because the participants in the study were principals and other school administrators. These considerations included maintaining confidentiality, maintaining anonymity, and preventing fraud. In addition, the people who participated in the study were given a debriefing so that they would not feel uneasy. Because part 1 of the research instrument gives the respondents the choice to divulge their names and other personal characteristics, the data that were collected during the study dealt with issues of confidentiality.

Results and Discussion

Profile of the Respondents

The first purpose of this research work was to the profile of the respondents in terms of birth order, sexual orientation, net take home pay and types of temperament.

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of School Leaders According to Variable Groupings

Variables	f	%
As a Whole	97	100
Birth Order		
Eldest Child	18	19
Middle Child	56	57
Youngest Child	21	22
Only Child	2	2
Sexual Orientation		
Male	21	22
Female	66	68
Gay	10	10

Take Home Pay

Php 5,000.00 to 25,500.00	80	82
Php 20,501.00 and Above	17	18
Types of Temperament		
Sanguine	62	64
Plegmatic	5	5
Melancholic	6	6
Choleric	24	25

Table 2 showed that the profile of the school leaders in terms of birth order encompassed 18 out of 97 school leaders who were the oldest child, 56 out of 97 school leaders who were the middle child, 21 out of 97 school leaders who were the youngest child, and the least number of school leaders who were only children, which only comprises 2 or 2% of the total respondents.

According to the profile of school leaders in terms of their sexual orientation, it was found that 21 out of 97, or 22%, of school leaders, were male, 66 out of 97, or 68%, of school leaders, were female, and 10 out of 97, or 10%, were gay. Regarding net take-home pay, 80 out of 97 school leaders, or 82%, belonged to the lower group, with the majority earning below \$25,000. per month, and 17 out of 97, or 18%, belonged to the higher group, with more than \$25,000 of their monthly compensation remaining.

In terms of various categories of temperament, 62 out of 97, or 63%, of the school leaders were considered to be sanguine types of individuals, 5 out of 97, or 5%, were choleric, 6 out of 97, or 6%, were melancholic, and 24 out of 97, or 24%, were considered to be phlegmatic kind of leaders.

It indicated that the majority of the school leaders in the Northern Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental were female and belonged to middle children. Additionally, they had a lower net monthly take-home pay and a sanguine temperament type. On the other hand, a smaller number of the school leaders were gay and only children, and they had a higher net take-home pay. Subsequently, they had a choleric temperament.

Level of Emotional Maturity of School Leaders

The second objective of the study concerns the level of emotional maturity of the school leaders when taken as a whole and grouped according to birth order, sexual orientation, net take-home pay and types of temperament.

The level of emotional maturity of school leaders was generally high, as demonstrated in Table 3 in the next page, with a mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.52.

When the respondents were categorized according to birth order, sexual orientation, net take-home pay, and types of temperament, they exhibited a "High" level of emotional maturity, with the mean ranging from 3.55 to 4.30.

Table 3

Level of Maturity of School Leaders When Taken As A Whole and Grouped According to Variable Groupings

Variables	Mean	SD	Interpretation
As a Whole	3.89	0.52	High
Birth Order			
Eldest Child	4.02	0.44	High
Middle Child	3.96	0.43	High
Youngest Child	3.55	0.66	High
Only Child	4.30	0.65	High
Sexual Orientation			

Male	3.94	0.45	High
Female	3.90	0.56	High
Gay	3.74	0.37	High
Take Home Pay			
Php 5,000.00 to 25,500.00	3.85	0.53	High
Php 20,501.00 and Above	4.06	0.44	High
Types of Temperament			
Sanguine	3.97	0.47	High
Phlegmatic	3.66	0.67	High
Melancholic	3.88	0.30	High
Choleric	3.68	0.31	High

Score Range	Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very High
3.50-4.49	High
2.50-3.49	Average
1.50-2.49	Low
1.00-1.49	Very Low

It implied that the majority of the school's leaders have a high level of emotional maturity in terms of their sexual preference, birth order, types of temperament, and monthly take-home pay. At all times, the school's leaders carried out their responsibilities as administrators of the school with a high degree of emotional tolerance and sensitivity to the needs of the students, teachers and all stakeholders.

The result was supported by Day and Carroll (2018), level of emotional maturity is not fixed genetically, nor does it develop only in early childhood. Unlike IQ, which changes little after our teen years, emotional intelligence seems to be largely learned, and it continues to develop as person go through life and learn from our experiences—person's competence in it can keep growing. In fact, studies that have tracked people's level of emotional intelligence/maturity through the years show that people get better and better in these capabilities as they grow more adept at handling their emotions and impulses, at motivating themselves, and at honing their empathy and social adroitness.

In addition, according to Bar-On (2020), who noted that this points out to the ability of the individual to notice his or her reactions and the reactions of other people and discriminate between the two through the experience not in sexual and chronological age of a person, and then utilize these observations as a guide for conduct and thinking. Emotional maturity is considered to be one of the many different types of mental ability.

The findings additionally offered support for the study conducted by Low and Nelson (2016), which argued that the role of emotion in a worker's health and success is essential. They came to the conclusion that an individual who possesses the skills associated with emotional intelligence is better able to deal with demanding and complicated work experiences. When people are able to successfully navigate their lives in the academic world, they are better able to concentrate on their studies and achieve better results

Conclusion:

Based on the findings of this investigation, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. It showed that female and middle-aged child made up the majority of the school leaders in the Northern Districts of the Division of Negros Occidental. They also had a sanguine temperament type and smaller net monthly take-home earnings. On the other side, fewer school administrators were in the LGBT and only-child groups, and they earn more take-home pay each month than average. They consequently have choleric temperaments.

2. In general, the leaders of the educational institution did a decent job of managing their sentiments and emotions in relation to their administrative careers. They demonstrated a great level of emotional maturity, not only in regard to their profession but also in all unanticipated situations that challenged their emotional well-being. As a direct consequence of this, they are able to carry out their obligations and responsibilities to an exceptionally high standard.

3. The school's administration was able to have a positive outlook and handle their emotions in a healthy way despite being under intense pressure, which helped them execute their tasks faster and better.

Leaders in schools are successful in all situations where human interaction is required because of their ability to maintain emotional equilibrium, maintain situational awareness, empathize with others' perspectives, inspire them to action, and interact with them in a socially acceptable manner. To exert effective authority over the classroom, they make it a point to ensure that all duties and responsibilities falling under their purview are effectively conveyed through the use of inspiring words and ideas. They may then make sure the school is being managed in the best possible way.

4. A leader at a school needs to be versatile and open-minded emotionally. This is because the management style of the school's leader has a significant bearing on the success of the institution as a whole. The intelligent and adaptable leadership at the school had a major impact on the institution's success because of its innovative approaches to problem-solving, decision-making, and other administrative duties. They can keep track of several components that are shifting at once and switch gears when necessary.

5. Many factors, including the need for timely report submission, overlapping activities, and teacher misconduct, contributed to the emotional and mental exhaustion of school administrators. However, they were able to potentially manage it by having a positive outlook, being flexible, being fair and sensitive in making decisions, and establishing rapport with others.

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